

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL MOUTHWASH WITH ANTIBACTERIAL, ANTIULCER AND MOUTH FRESHENING ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Herbal medicinal plants are considered a rich source of bioactive constituents useful in the development of safe and effective oral care formulations. The present work focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a polyherbal mouthwash containing guava leaves extract, pomegranate extract, tulsi extract, and liquorice extract for the management of oral ulcers and maintenance of oral hygiene. These herbal ingredients possess antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, wound healing, and soothing properties that help reduce oral irritation, promote ulcer healing, control microbial growth, and provide long-lasting freshness to the oral cavity. The formulated herbal mouthwash is intended as a natural alternative to chemical-based mouthwashes, which may cause irritation or sensitivity with prolonged use. The combination of herbal extracts also helps in reducing plaque formation, maintaining healthy gums, freshening breath, and improving overall oral hygiene. The

prepared formulation was evaluated for various physicochemical parameters including pH, stability, appearance and antimicrobial activity. The results indicated satisfactory stability and significant antimicrobial effectiveness against oral microorganisms, suggesting that the herbal mouthwash can serve as a safe, effective, and economical approach for oral ulcer

management and oral healthcare.

KEYWORDS: Herbal mouthwash, Antimicrobial Activity, Oral Cavity.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, oral health is increasingly recognized as a significant issue. The World Oral Health Report 2003 emphasized that oral health is a vital and fundamental aspect of overall health. Most chemical products include an antiseptic that is crucial for managing plaque buildup. The means of delivering chemical agents with antiplaque properties include toothpaste, mouthwashes, sprays, irrigators, chewing gums, and varnishes. Nevertheless, the most widely accepted method for administering antimicrobial agents after toothpaste is mouthwash. Mouthwashes are antiseptic solutions utilized to diminish the microbial load in the oral cavity. These liquids contain antiinflammatory, antimicrobial, and analgesic properties. There are two categories of mouthwashes: chemical and herbal. Herbal mouthwashes consist of natural ingredients known as phytochemicals, which provide the desired antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory benefits. As herbal mouthwashes gain popularity, they are preferred for their alcohol-free formulation.^[1]

Artificial preservatives, flavors, and colors are present. This product includes natural herbs that possess inherent cleansing and healing properties for teeth and gums.^[2] Numerous herbal mouthwashes incorporate herbs with antimicrobial properties, such as guava, pomegranate, cinnamon oil, and clove. Among the herbs utilized in mouthwashes is clove, which has been traditionally recognized for its benefits to oral health due to its antiseptic, antibacterial, and antiviral properties. Peppermint is also included for its cooling effect on the mouth.^[3] Natural herbs like guava, tulsi, pomegranate, clove oil, and pudina, whether used individually or in combination, have been scientifically validated as safe and effective remedies for oral health issues, including bleeding gums, mouth ulcers, and the prevention of tooth decay, all without side effects. In contrast, nearly all chemical mouthwashes contain alcohol and fluoride, which can be toxic to the body in excessive amounts.^[4] Therefore, most herbal mouthwashes represent a safe alternative for pregnant women, individuals with dry mouths, diabetics, and children. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of mouthwash usage, focusing not only on the type of mouthwash but also on the quantity used, which is equally significant. Additionally, this research was conducted to evaluate the efficacy and safety of herbal mouthwash for human medicinal use.^[5]

HERBAL MOUTHWASH

A herbal mouthwash is an oral hygiene liquid made from natural plant-based ingredients recognized for their medicinal benefits. In contrast to traditional mouthwashes that frequently include alcohol, chlorhexidine, or synthetic antiseptics, herbal mouthwashes utilize herbal extracts, essential oils, and other natural components like guava, tulsi, pomegranate, licorice, and peppermint oil to support oral health. These natural elements provide antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antioxidant, and soothing properties that assist in preventing dental plaque, gingivitis, halitosis (bad breath), and various other oral infections.^[2]

History of Mouthwash

1. Ancient Use (Around 2700 BCE): The earliest known Use of mouth rinses dates back to ancient Chinese and Indian civilizations, where herbal mixtures were used for Oral hygiene
2. Greco-Roman Era: The Greeks and Romans used Mouth rinses made of salt and vinegar. Hippocrates Recommended a mixture of salt, alum, and vinegar for Cleaning the mouth.
3. Medieval Period: Mouth rinsing practices continued With the use of herbal infusions, wine, or even urine (believed to have cleansing properties).
4. 18th Century: Mouthwash began to be recognized in Europe as a commercial product, often alcohol-based and Used for both oral hygiene and breath freshening.
5. Modern Era (19th-20th Century): The invention of Antiseptic solutions like Listerine in the late 1800s Revolutionized mouthwash use, making it a regular part of Oral hygiene routines worldwide.^[4]

Benefits of using a herbal mouthwash

1. Natural Ingredients: Made from plant-based herbs and Phytochemicals.
2. Antimicrobial Action: Helps kill or reduce harmful oral Bacteria.
3. Anti-inflammatory Properties: Soothes inflamed gums And reduces swelling.
4. No Alcohol: Safer for people with dry mouth, children, And pregnant women.
5. Fewer Side Effects: Less likely to cause staining, Burning sensation, or taste alteration compared to Chemical mouthwashes.
6. Promotes Healing: Supports natural healing of mouth Ulcers, wounds, and gum issues.
7. Prevents Dental Problems: Reduces risk of plaque, Gingivitis, bad breath, and tooth decay.
8. Eco-Friendly: Biodegradable and generally safer for the Environment.
9. No Artificial Additives: Free from synthetic Preservatives, flavors, and colors.

10. Long-term Use: Safe and gentle for daily, long-term oral Care.^[5]

How to use herbal mouthwash

Take 10-15 ml mouthwash and gargle it for 30 sec and rinse it

Litratue Survey

1. Shailesh Rote et al. (2025)– Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Mouthwash Shailesh Rote and co-authors carried out a study on the formulation and evaluation of herbal mouthwash using natural plant extracts with antimicrobial activity. The study focused on preparing an alcohol-free herbal mouthwash effective against oral microorganisms responsible for dental plaque, bad breath, and gum infections. Various herbal ingredients possessing antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties were incorporated into the formulation. The prepared mouthwash was evaluated for parameters such as pH, color, odor, stability, viscosity, and antimicrobial activity. The results showed that the herbal mouthwash exhibited significant inhibitory effects against oral pathogens and was considered safe and effective for maintaining oral hygiene.

2. Deep Patel, Jainil Patel et al. (2025)– Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Mouthwash (JETIR, 2025) Deep Patel, Jainil Patel, and co-authors published a research article in the Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR) in 2025 on the formulation and evaluation of herbal mouthwash. The objective of the study was to develop a herbal mouthwash using medicinal plant extracts as an alternative to synthetic mouthwashes containing alcohol and chemical agents. The prepared formulation was evaluated for physical appearance, pH, stability, and antimicrobial activity against oral bacteria. The study reported that herbal ingredients effectively reduced microbial growth and provided good cleansing action with minimal side effects. The research concluded that herbal mouthwash can be a safe, economical, and effective approach for oral healthcare management.

3. Ukirde K.P., Arote S.S. et al. (2022)– A Review on Herbal Mouthwash: A Natural Approach to Oral Care Ukirde K.P., Arote S.S., and co-authors presented a review article on herbal mouthwash as a natural approach to oral care. The review discussed the importance of herbal formulations in preventing oral diseases such as dental caries, gingivitis, plaque formation, and halitosis. Different medicinal plants including neem, tulsi, clove, licorice, and guava were highlighted for their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties. The authors compared herbal mouthwashes with synthetic formulations and explained that herbal preparations have fewer side effects and better patient acceptability. The review concluded

that herbal mouthwash formulations are promising alternatives for maintaining oral hygiene and improving oral health naturally.

4. Govardhan et al. (2023) - developed and evaluated an antibacterial herbal mouthwash against oral pathogens. The formulation showed effective antimicrobial activity against *Streptococcus mutans* and *Streptococcus salivarius*, with good zones of inhibition. The study concluded that herbal mouthwash can help reduce plaque, bad breath, and oral infections with fewer side effects than chemical mouthwashes.

DRUG PROFILE AND EXCIPIENT

1. Guava Leaves Extract

Synonym: Psidii folium

Biological Name: *Psidium guajava*

Family: Myrtaceae

Chemical Constituents: Guava leaf extract contains flavonoids, tannins, saponins, quercetin, and essential oils. These constituents possess antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antiinflammatory properties. They are responsible for the therapeutic activity of guava leaf extract.^[8]

Uses

1. Antibacterial – Prevent oral infection.
2. Anti- inflammatory – Reduces swelling and pain
3. Anti- ulcer- Helpful in mouth ulcers

2. Pomegranate Extract

Synonym: *Malum Punicum* (latin), Pomegranate

Biological Name: *Punica granatum* linn

Family: Lythraceae

Chemical Constituents: Pomegranate peel extract contains tannins, flavonoids, polyphenols, punicalagin, and ellagic acid. These constituents possess antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antiinflammatory properties.

Uses

1. Antibacterial – Prevent oral infection.
- Reduces gum inflammation and bleeding gums Strong antioxidant activity.^[8]

3. Tulsi Extract

Synonyms: Holy basil, Sacred basil, Tulsi

Biological Name: *Ocimum sanctum* / *Ocimum tenuiflorum*

Family: Lamiaceae

Chemical Constituents: Tulsi extract contains eugenol, ursolic acid, flavonoids, tannins, and essential oils. These constituents show antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities.

Uses

Helps reduce bad breath (halitosis)

Fights bacteria causing plaque and cavities Helps in gum inflammation and bleeding gums

Gives a refreshing feeling in the mouth.^[9]

4. Liquorice Extract

Synonym: liquorice / licorice, Mulethi (hindi)

Biological Name: *Glycyrrhiza glabra* linn

Family: Fabaceae (Leguminosae)

Chemical Constituents: Liquorice extract contains glycyrrhizin, flavonoids, saponins, and chalcones. These constituents exhibit antimicrobial, soothing, and anti-inflammatory properties.^[9]

Uses

Improves flavor and sweetness. Enhances antimicrobial action.

Gives soothing effect to oral tissues. Help to reduce bad breath.

5. Beetroot Powder **Synonym:** Beet, Red beet

Biological Name: *Beta Vulgaris*

Family: Amaranthacea **Chemical Constituents:** Beetroot powder contains betalains, nitrates, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and vitamins. These constituents possess antioxidant, antimicrobial, and coloring properties.

Uses

Antioxidant activity Mild antimicrobial effect

Natural coloring agent

Improving appearance of herbal mouthwash^[10]

6. Peppermint Oil

Synonym: Mentha Piperita

Biological Name: Mentha Piperita linn

Family: Lamiaceae

Chemical Constituents: Peppermint oil contains major chemical constituents such as menthol, menthone, menthyl acetate, and cineole. These compounds provide antimicrobial, cooling, and refreshing properties. Therefore, peppermint oil is widely used in mouthwash formulations to improve oral hygiene and freshen breath.

Uses

Peppermint oil shows antimicrobial activity against oral bacteria. It helps in freshening breath and reducing bad odor.

It provides a cooling and soothing sensation in the mouth. It improves the taste and acceptability of mouthwash.^[10]

7. Sodium Benzoate

Sodium benzoate is mainly used in mouthwash as a preservative. It helps prevent the growth of bacteria, fungi, and other microorganisms in the formulation, thereby increasing the shelf life and maintaining the stability of the mouthwash. It also helps keep the product safe and effective during storage and regular use.^[1]

8. Polysorbate 20 (Tween 20) I

Polysorbate 20 is used in mouthwash as a solubilizing and emulsifying agent. It helps mix essential oils, flavors, and other oil-based ingredients uniformly in water, improving the clarity, stability, and consistency of the mouthwash formulation. It also enhances the distribution of active ingredients throughout the solution.^[1]

9. Citric Acid

Citric acid is used in mouthwash as a pH adjusting and flavor-enhancing agent. It helps maintain the acidity and stability of the formulation, improves taste, and supports the effectiveness of other ingredients. It also provides a refreshing sensation and helps in maintaining oral hygiene.^[11]

METHOD OF EXTRACTION

1. Procedure of Guava Leaves Extract

Fresh guava leaves were collected from the Botanical Garden and subjected to sun drying for

approximately three days. The dried leaves were then ground into a coarse powder to facilitate the extraction process. For the preparation of the hot aqueous extract, 25 g of the powdered material was mixed with 200 mL of sterile double-distilled water in a beaker. The mixture was heated on a water bath until the volume was reduced to below 50 mL. The obtained extract was subsequently filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 1 to obtain a clear filtrate.^[7]

2. Preparation of Pomegranate Peel Extract

Pomegranate peels were dried in sunlight followed by drying in a hot air oven at 60°C for 7 days. The dried peels were then powdered using a grinder. The obtained powder was used to prepare an aqueous extract by the maceration method. About 25 g of peel powder was soaked in 200 ml of distilled water and kept for 24 hours with occasional stirring. The mixture was then filtered using muslin cloth and Whatman filter paper to obtain the aqueous extract.^[9]

3. Preparation of Tulsi Extract

Fresh leaves of Tulsi were collected, washed thoroughly with distilled water, and shade dried for 5–7 days. The dried leaves were powdered using a grinder. About 25 g of Tulsi leaf powder was soaked in 200 ml of distilled water and kept for 24 hours at room temperature with occasional stirring (maceration method). The mixture was then filtered using muslin cloth followed by Whatman filter paper to obtain the aqueous extract.^[9]

4. Preparation of Liquorice Extract

Dried liquorice roots were powdered and extracted with distilled water by decoction method. About 25 g of powder was boiled with 200 mL distilled water for 30–45 minutes. The extract was cooled, filtered, and stored in an airtight container for further use.^[10]

Material Used

Guava leaves extract, Pomegranate extract, Tulsi extract, Liquirice extract, Beetroot Powder, Peppermint oil, Sodium benzoate, Polysorbate 20, Citric acid.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

1. Take approximately 30 mL of purified water in a clean and dry beaker.
2. Add 0.1 g sodium benzoate and 0.15 g citric acid into the water and stir properly until completely dissolved.
3. Add guava leaves extract, pomegranate extract, and tulsi extract into the above

solution with continuous stirring.

4. Add liquorice extract and mix until a uniform solution is obtained.
5. Add beetroot powder solution slowly to impart natural color and stir well.
6. In a separate beaker, dissolve peppermint oil in polysorbate 20 to obtain a clear and uniform mixture.
7. Add the prepared peppermint oil mixture slowly into the herbal solution with continuous stirring.
8. Add purified water gradually to make up the final volume to 50 mL.
9. Stir the final formulation continuously for about 10–15 minutes to obtain a homogeneous mouthwash.
10. Filter the formulation using muslin cloth or filter paper to remove any particulate matter.
11. Transfer the prepared herbal mouthwash into a clean, airtight amber-colored bottle and label properly.
12. Store the formulation at room temperature away from direct sunlight

Fig. no. 11: Formulation Of Herbal Mouthwash.

Formulation of Herbal Mouthwash

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Guava leaves extract	0.5ml	2ml	0.5ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	2ml
Pomegranate extract	0.5ml	1ml	1ml	0.5ml	1ml	1ml	2ml	1ml	1ml
Tulsi extract	0.5ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	0.5ml	1ml	1ml	2ml	1ml
Liquorice extract	0.5ml								
Beetroot Powder	0.2ml	0.1ml							
Peppermint oil	2-3 drop	5 drop	4 drop	4 drop	4 drop	4 drop	5 drop	5 drop	5 drop
Sodium benzoate	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g	0.1 g	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g
Polysorbate 20	0.5ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml
Citric acid	0.15g								
Purified water	q.s. 50ml								

EVALUATION PARAMETER OF HERBAL MOUTHWASH

It is very essential to maintain a uniform standard for herbal mouthwash keeping view in mind the formulated herbal mouthwash was evaluated on the parameters.

1. Physical Evaluation

Physical parameter such as color, odour, taste and consistency were examined by visual Examination.

2. pH Test

Fig. no. 12: pH meter.

pH of prepared herbal mouthwash was measured by using digital pH meter. The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solution about 1 ml of mouthwash was weighed and dissolved in 50ml of distilled water and its pH was measured.^[12]

3. Determination of Antibacterial Activity of Herbal Mouthwash

The antibacterial activity of the formulated herbal mouthwash was evaluated by the agar well diffusion method against *Streptococcus mutans* and *Escherichia coli*. Fresh bacterial cultures were prepared in nutrient broth and incubated at 37 °C for 48 hours. Sterile nutrient agar plates were inoculated with 0.05 mL of bacterial culture using a sterile spreader. Wells were made in the agar using a sterile cork borer, and 0.05 mL of herbal mouthwash was added into each well. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours, and the zone of inhibition around the wells was measured to determine antibacterial activity.^[13]

Fig. no. 13: Test for antimicrobial activity.

4. Skin Irritation Test

The irritancy test was performed on the herbal formulation. There is no redness or irritancy in the Preparation. The condition was seen for 24 hrs.^[12]

5. Foam Ability Test

To determine the foam-forming ability of the herbal mouthwash, about 1 g of mouthwash was mixed with 50 mL of distilled water in a 100 mL measuring cylinder. The cylinder was shaken well for 10 minutes to produce foam. After 10 minutes, the height of the foam was measured. The test was repeated five times, and the average value was recorded.^[14]

6. Stability Test

The formulation was stored at room temperature and observed for changes in color, odor, pH, and precipitation over a specific period to evaluate stability.^[14]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

SR	Evaluation Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1.	Colour & Texture	Light pink	Pink	Light red	Pink	Reddish pink	Clear reddish pink	Pink	Dark pink	Reddish Brown
2.	pH	5.8	6.1	6.0	6.2	6.3	6.5	6.4	6.5	6.2
3.	Microbial test	No microbial growth								
4.	Foam ability	Moderate foam	Good foam	Moderate foam	Good foam	Good foam	Excellent foam	High foam	High foam	High foam
5.	Skin Irritation test	No irritation	Mild irritation	Mild irritation	Mild irritation					
6.	Stability test	Stable								

DISCUSSION

All formulated herbal mouthwash batches (F1–F9) showed satisfactory results for color, pH, microbial test, foam ability, skin irritation, and stability. The formulations showed acceptable appearance with pH in the suitable range for oral use. No microbial growth was observed in any batch, indicating good antimicrobial activity and preservative effectiveness. All batches were stable and non-irritant. Among all formulations, batch **F6** showed the best overall performance with clear reddish-pink appearance, ideal pH (6.5), excellent foam ability, no irritation, no microbial growth, and good stability. Therefore, **F6** was considered the optimized and successfully passed formulation.

CONCLUSION

The herbal mouthwash was successfully formulated and evaluated using natural herbal extracts. The formulation showed good antimicrobial activity, stability, safety, and acceptable

physicochemical properties. Among all batches, F6 was found to be the best formulation due to its excellent overall evaluation results. The study concluded that the prepared herbal mouthwash can be used as a safe, effective, and natural alternative for maintaining oral hygiene and reducing oral infection.

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